

Reverse Engineering for Input Modeling: Input Parameter Model Inference from Network Traces

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Abstract. Combinatorial testing is a model-based testing methodology that offers mathematical guarantees about the coverage of the input space of a system under test. At the same time, it aims to minimize the number of required test cases, leading to faster execution of test sets. However, input parameter models are often not available in real-world settings; they require significant investment to create and maintain. For proprietary protocols, specifications are often not freely available at all. It thus seems prudent to enable practitioners to infer input parameter models from the system under test without relying on the availability of source code or detailed documentation. This work aims to allow testers, developers, and researchers to reverse engineer the format of unknown network protocols based on traffic traces, generate input parameter models suitable for use in combinatorial testing from this inferred specification, and translate abstract test sets represented by covering arrays to concrete messages that can subsequently be transmitted over the network. It is the first work to investigate the combination of protocol reverse engineering with automated input parameter modeling for combinatorial testing.

Keywords: Combinatorial Testing · Protocol Reverse Engineering · Input Parameter Model

1 Introduction

Software testing is one of the most important aspects of a contemporary software development lifecycle (SDLC). It verifies that a particular piece of software exhibits the correct behavior when confronted with some input, commonly called the *test case*. A variety of testing approaches exists, each offering a particular set of advantages and drawbacks. Examples include unit tests, fuzz testing, and model-based testing [1].

Model-based testing requires a model of the input space of the system under test (SUT). In contrast to unit tests and fuzz testing, it can offer guarantees about the input space coverage; in combinatorial testing (CT) (see Section 2.1), which is the primary focus of this work, the tester chooses a *strength* t . Under certain assumptions, CT guarantees that all faults that can be triggered by a combination of t parameters or less will be found. However, creating and maintaining the required model of the SUT’s input space commonly leads to significant manual effort and is rarely performed as part of the SDLC. Additionally, constructing an accurate model for legacy or proprietary SUTs without access to the source code is challenging.

This work investigates an alternative approach to create an input parameter model (IPM) for use in CT with a focus on binary network protocols. Through the use of protocol reverse engineering (PRE) techniques applicable to network traces, we infer an IPM capturing the structure of transmitted messages. Applying the techniques presented in this work results in a model suitable for the generation of combinatorial test sets, enabling practitioners to use CT to identify vulnerabilities and verify that protocol implementations handle incoming messages correctly. We seek to answer the following **research questions**:

- I. How can primitive types with extensive domains encountered in the context of network protocols be modeled for the purposes of combinatorial testing?
- II. How can idioms such as length-value fields, repetitions and offsets be translated to a notion of constrained IPMs suitable for combinatorial test generation?

The primary **contribution** of our work is a practical approach that combines PRE with input parameter modeling for CT. It additionally enables the translation of generated abstract test sets to concrete messages that can then be submitted to the SUT. A Python implementation based on Netzob [5] is provided as open source software⁴. Note that the acquisition of suitable network traffic traces is not within the scope of our work.

The remainder of this work is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces CT and its underlying mathematical structures as well as the testing workflow commonly utilized when applying it to software and the notions underlying protocol reverse engineering. Subsequently, Section 3 outlines the most important pieces of related work. Section 4 introduces our methodology and the steps required to apply it to real-world network protocols, followed by an example based on a popular file transfer protocol. Finally, Section 5 summarizes our contributions, outlines the most important results, and provides directions for future work.

2 Preliminaries

This section serves to familiarise readers with the basic notions, notations and workflows in the areas of combinatorial testing and protocol reverse engineering.

⁴ Available at <https://co.redacted.is/netzob-master.zip>.

2.1 Combinatorial Testing

In most testing approaches, **test cases** are submitted to the SUT [1,18]. A SUT is some abstract system that takes an input consisting of one or more parameters, each of which can assume one value out of a list of parameter values. The parameters and their possible values are described in an **input model**. A **test case** assigns specific values to each parameter. It thus describes the input submitted to the SUT. The set of test cases used in a testing process is called the **test set**. Once a test case is submitted, an **oracle** decides whether the SUT behaved correctly. The precise definition of correct behavior depends on the SUT, the available output, and the goals of the testing process.

Combinatorial testing is a model-based testing methodology that takes a model of the input space of an SUT as its input and generates a test set that offers mathematical guarantees about its input space coverage [18] based on parameter-value combinations. Assume that a SUT accepts some input made up of $k > 1$ parameters and that the parameter with the index i can take values in the set $\{1, \dots, v_i\}$. The underlying mathematical structure behind CT as used in our work is a **mixed-level covering array** $MCA(N; t, k, \{v_1, \dots, v_k\})$, an array with N rows (representing test cases) and k columns (corresponding to parameters). The defining property of a MCA is that for every possible selection of t distinct parameters, all possible parameter-value combinations occur at least in one row in the array. Increasing the value of t leads to a larger array (because more parameter-value combinations must be covered), but also to better fault detection capabilities. Accordingly, we call t the *combinatorial strength*. Note that in most theoretical works, a $CA(N; t, k, v)$ is used instead of an MCA, the only difference being the uniform alphabet of size v . For the sake of brevity, we call both variants a CA in this work.

Compared to fully exhaustive testing, CT results in a drastic reduction in the number of test cases. Intuitively, this should also allow us to find less flaws. However, in multiple studies investigating known bugs across different industries, NIST was unable to identify any faults that were caused by the interaction of more than 6 parameters [19]. In some industries, the maximum number of parameters implicated in a single faulty interaction was 4. This indicates that in practice, the value of t necessary to identify all (or almost all) bugs is rather small.

Workflow. The general CT workflow encompasses the following steps [27,12]:

1. **Input Modeling.** In this step, an IPM is created, describing the inputs that are accepted by the SUT. Additionally, constraints may be imposed. An example IPM compatible with the CA generator PICT [9] is given in Listing 1.1. This model describes configurations of a phone, in particular whether the phone offers an email viewer (**emailViewer**), how many lines of text can be displayed (**textLines**) and how many colors are supported (**display**). Additionally, a single constraint exists: If the phone has an email viewer, the **textLines** parameter must be set to a value greater than 28.

```

emailViewer: TRUE, FALSE
textLines: 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30
display: 16MC, 8MC, BW
IF [emailViewer] = "TRUE" THEN [textLines] > 28;

```

Listing 1.1: Example IPM.

2. **Test Generation.** This step passes the IPM, constraints, and strength to a CA generator. The resulting array commonly consists of rows made up of abstract values. A **translation** is thus required in order to construct concrete files, protocol messages, or other input accepted by the SUT.
3. **Test Execution.** Here, the translated test cases are submitted to the SUT and its output collected.
4. **Test Oracle.** The task of the oracle is to use the output of the SUT and decide whether it handled the test case correctly.

2.2 Protocol Reverse Engineering

Network protocols define rules regarding the communication between multiple entities. A protocol commonly specifies the syntax and semantics of individual pieces of information transmitted between participants, as well as rules regarding the behaviour of such peers. The goal of network PRE is to recover these rules and definitions for an unknown network protocol.

The terminology used in the literature differs slightly, even between contemporary surveys [26,16,10]. As stated in a recent survey [26], a *message* is an application-level unit of data exchanged between two communication partners (commonly a client and server). Messages may be grouped into *classes*, identified by a *type* [10]. Messages conform to a protocol or message *syntax* and are made up of *fields* [26], which are contiguous bytes. Fields can be static or variable (indicating whether their content varies between messages of the same type), and variable fields can have fixed or variable length. In addition to the syntax of individual messages, most protocols require some form of state machine to implement stateful handling of messages, a topic we regard as future work.

The two primary types of input are *network traces* [26,20] and *execution traces* [26]. Network traces consist of data that is transmitted between communication peers (e.g. IP packets or TCP flows). Execution traces are acquired by monitoring a program implementing a protocol and extracting data that indicate how protocol messages are processed. In this work, we focus exclusively on network trace analysis due to the extensive instrumentation effort required to obtain suitable execution traces. However, note that protocols using encryption or compression may render network traces unsuitable for PRE.

3 Related Work

Our work combines two areas of research: Input parameter modeling and protocol reverse engineering. This section describes previous work that relates to the goals of our approach.

3.1 Input parameter modeling for CT

We were unable to identify any prior work that specifically targets input parameter modeling for CT using reverse engineering methods. All related work in the literature seems to derive an input model from source code, existing specifications, documents, or models, or expert interviews.

An early work on automated software testing [22] describes the use of category partitioning to specify and generate functional tests. Similarly, the method described by Grochtmann and Grimm [13] aims to create test cases not by combinatorial means, but by classifying the values of each parameter semantically into disjoint partitions. A more comprehensive overview of this approach and related techniques is given by Ammann and Offutt [1]. A related approach is boundary value analysis [23]. Intuitively speaking, the disjoint partitions of the domain of a parameter mentioned above are always defined by their boundaries. Software issues such as off-by-one bugs tend to arise from inconsistencies around the boundaries of equivalence partitions, so it makes sense to include tests that exercise these values as well as their immediate “neighborhood”. Note that some values may be considered invalid; they can be excluded or marked as *negative values* [9], which must be handled accordingly by the testing oracle.

A method to model composed systems for combinatorial testing is given by Kampel et al. [14]; a similar concept called input structure modeling [4] describes hierarchical relations between parameters using graphs. To aid testers in successfully tackling more complex situations while modeling, Segall et al. [24] explore common patterns in combinatorial models and gives recipes for formulating optional and conditional values, ranges and boundaries, order and padding, and multiplicities. Another work by the same authors [25] proposes two extensions to IPMs in general: A new type of parameter called a *counter* and the ability for parameters to have *properties*.

3.2 Protocol reverse engineering

A 2004 work by Marshall A. Beddoe [3] is widely considered one of the first academic works on PRE. It presents algorithms from bioinformatics and discusses their use in the context of protocols. In total, four techniques are discussed:

1. Global sequence alignment using the Needleman-Wunsch algorithm [21];
2. local sequence alignment based on the Smith-Waterman algorithm [28];
3. the use of similarity matrices in the context of these sequence alignment techniques;
4. multiple sequence alignment using phylogenetic trees constructed using the Unweighted Pairwise Mean by Arithmetic Averages (UPGMA) algorithm [29].

A wide range of works have built and improved upon this initial approach, often adopting the underlying techniques for various purposes. While Role-Player [8] aims to allow for adaptive replay of application sessions, keeping the overall flow and meaning of communication intact while incorporating dynamic fields that differ between sessions, Discoverer [7] is a dedicated approach geared

Fig. 1: Overview of the approach presented in this work

towards PRE. It introduces the concept of a *Format Distinguisher (FD)*, a field that serves to differentiate between the possible formats of the subsequent parts of a message. The goal of AutoFuzz [11] is to enable automated fuzz testing of unknown network protocols. It infers both a FSM of the protocol behavior and a model of the protocol syntax. While most approaches reviewed previously tend to focus on heuristics, ASAP [17] uses vector spaces and matrices to infer *semantic templates* of exchanged messages. Unfortunately, they do not encode the ordering of tokens; accordingly, ASAP is not suitable for our purposes. Whalen et al. [32] infer hidden Markov models (HMMs) to describe the syntax of messages. In contrast, ReverX [2] aims to infer two machines from network traffic, one describing the message format and the other detailing the protocol behavior, by utilizing a type of state machine called a Prefix Tree Acceptor.

Netzob [5] is one of the most pragmatic and simultaneously unusual approaches reviewed herein. It offers an interactive toolkit that enables users to perform semi-automated PRE based on the definition of abstract actions (e.g. “list directory”) and contextual data (such as IP addresses). In contrast to most other works in the field of PRE, Netzob is available as open source software.

The authors of PRE-Bin [31] aim to specifically address the challenges of reverse engineering binary protocols, particularly those where individual fields may be smaller than a byte. It focuses on identifying field boundaries and does not attempt to infer field types. Similarly, NEMESYS [15] aims to determine field boundaries; however, unlike all previously seen approaches, it only requires a single message of each type to do so.

In many cases, a combination of clustering techniques, classifiers, and user feedback (or configuration) seems to be the toolset of choice for binary protocol reverse engineering based on traffic traces.

4 Methodology

Due to its versatility, robust codebase and availability as open source software, we decided to use Netzob as the basis for our approach, an overview of which is visualized in Figure 1. The phases can be summarized as follows:

1. **Protocol Trace Generation.** A network trace is generated, commonly by recording existing network traffic.
2. **Format Inference.** The protocol message format is inferred from the traffic trace, generating a description in the Netzob-internal format described in Section 4.1.
3. **Boundary Value Determination.** To derive values for the individual fields in each message, we model them using boundary value analysis, depending on the type of each field and runtime properties (see Section 4.2).
4. **Input Parameter Model Generation.** After establishing symbolic boundary values for each of the primitive variables encountered in a message format, they must be combined into fields and ultimately a complete abstract definition of a message. An in-depth description of this step is provided in Section 4.3.
5. **Covering Array Generation.** As the output of the previous step consists of one or more IPMs, a dedicated CA generation tool is subsequently applied to derive abstract CAs with a requested strength. In the current version, support is limited to PICT [9].
6. **Covering Array Translation.** In this step, the message format is used in combination with the generated CAs in order to derive concrete messages as described in Section 4.4.

4.1 Netzob message format

This section summarizes and extends the first chapter of the Netzob Language Specifications documentation⁵.

The format of all messages of a protocol is described as a set of *symbols*, with each symbol describing a particular message format. A symbol is made up of a sequence of *fields* and the domain of a field is described by a tree. This tree consists of *variables*; specifically, there exist *node variables* which can accept one or more children, and *leaf variables*, which can not accept any children.

Fig. 2: Netzob symbol structure.

⁵ <https://gdr-securite.irisa.fr/wp-content/uploads/sujet17-amossys.pdf>

Figure 2 provides an example of the structure of a symbol. The following kinds of node variables exist:

- **Agg**, the *aggregate node variable*, a concatenation of its child nodes.
- **Alt**, the *alternative node variable*, which encodes that exactly one of its child nodes shall be used. Figure 2 shows an example where either an ASCII data variable or a timestamp are permitted.
- **Repeat**, the *repetition node variable*, which must have exactly one child. It defines that this child node shall be repeated a certain number of times. The number of repetitions can be defined in different ways: Either as a single integer, a tuple defining the minimum and maximum number of repetitions, a field that is considered a terminator when parsing a message, or a Python function. The latter two versions are not suitable for our approach. Figure 2 contains an example where the aforementioned alternative node variable can be repeated multiple times.

Leaf variables can be either *relationship variables* or *data variables* (which are called *primitive types* in this work). Relationship variables specify a variable that derives its value based on that of another variable. This includes computed checksums, variables that derive their value from the size of other fields (as shown in Figure 2), and custom Python functions that compute their value based on other fields. Data variables encode primitive data types. Because they must be capable of encoding their value to raw bits, all these variables have the following properties:

- The current value of this variable;
- the encoded size of this variable in bits; commonly a range defined by the minimum and maximum number of bits (which may be identical);
- The unit size, i.e. the number of bits of a single “unit” of this type (for instance a single character);
- The endianness of the encoded representation;
- The signedness of the data type; this is only relevant for numeric types.

Some of the available types define additional properties. The available primitive types are the following:

- **Integer**, a numeric value. This type additionally accepts an interval defining its minimum and maximum value, which is not stored in Netzob. We modify the code to additionally store the interval as a basis for IPM construction.
- **HexaString**, binary data specified as a hexadecimal string.
- **Raw**, binary data expressed as raw bytes. This type defines two additional properties: A minimum and maximum size in bytes, and an optional alphabet of allowed values for this type.
- **BitArray**, binary data expressed as raw bits.
- **IPv4**, a 32 bit IP address. It defines one additional property that allows the definition of an allowed network. If the network is not defined, the default generation method in Netzob instead picks a random address in a random non-private network.

- **ASCII**, a string type. This type additionally defines a property that allows the specification of a minimum and maximum length.
- **Timestamp**, used to store an integer along with information on the epoch (the meaning of the value 0, e.g. 1970-01-01 00:00:00 for UNIX time) and a unit (the meaning of a unit change in the integer value, e.g. second, nanosecond, or minute).

4.2 Boundary values

While the protocol message format inferred by Netzob described above describes the structure of the message in sufficient detail, we are faced with a common problem in modeling when attempting to create an IPM for combinatorial testing: In general, it is infeasible to comprehensively test the entire value domain of each variable. This issue is reflected in our first **Research Question**.

To alleviate this problem, we use the boundaries of partitions of the value domain of each variable, as well as their immediate neighborhood, to model the domain in a symbolic manner.

We model the domain of each variable as the combination of one or more symbolic parameters. In the Covering Array Translation step, we then use these parameters to derive a concrete value for the variable. Variables with a fixed value are not reflected in the IPM; we assume that changing their value will cause the protocol to no longer be parsed correctly. For the same reason, we do not violate the size constraints laid forth in the protocol specification; however, we do use invalid values and values that are likely to lead to faulty processing, determined by expert knowledge. For all non-constant variables, their *size* - assuming it is not fixed, but represented by a minimum and maximum value - is modeled using the boundary values `SIZE_MIN`, `SIZE_MAX` and `SIZE_RAND`. While the former two represent the minimum and maximum size for this type, the latter is some random value between the minimum and maximum size. It is omitted if the difference is less than 2.

The size is the first IPM parameter for a data variable. The following paragraphs detail additional boundary values (represented by additional parameters in the IPM) for the respective types. We denote invalid boundary values through the use of an exclamation mark.

Integer If no minimum and maximum value are given, we instead use the smallest and largest value that can be represented given the variable's signedness and bit size to define an interval. As boundary values, we model the minimum (`VALUE_MIN`) and maximum (`VALUE_MAX`) value according to the interval as well as their neighbors. The valid neighbors `VALUE_MIN_PLUS` and `VALUE_MAX_MINUS` represent the minimum value plus one and the maximum value minus one, respectively. We additionally model the invalid neighbors `!VALUE_MIN_MINUS` and `!VALUE_MAX_PLUS`, with the former representing the minimum value minus one and the latter signifying the maximum value plus one (these values are omitted if

they can not be represented by the data type). Finally, we add a symbolic value `VALUE_RAND`, which will be translated to a random value between the minimum value plus one and the maximum value minus one. If the difference between the minimum and maximum is less than 4, this symbol is omitted.

HexString, BitArray Both `HexString` and `BitArray` express an arbitrary sequence of bits with the given length constraints. The boundary values `VALUE_NONE` and `VALUE_ALL` represent all-zero and all-one bit assignments. If the length l (representing the field’s size in bits) is greater than 1, `VALUE_MSB` and `VALUE_LSB` indicate all-zero values with only the most or least significant bit set. If $l > 2$, we additionally add `VALUE_RAND`, a random value that is guaranteed to not be equal to any of the other boundary values, as well as `VALUE_BOTTOMHALF`, where the least significant $\lceil l/2 \rceil$ bits are set to one and all others to zero. Finally, if $l > 3$, we introduce the counterpart `VALUE_TOPHALF`, which sets the most significant $\lfloor l/2 \rfloor$ bits to one.

Raw Similar to `HexString` and `BitArray`, this type often expresses an arbitrary sequence of bits. We thus reuse their boundary values mentioned above. However, a `Raw` variable may additionally have an alphabet, which is a list of allowed unit values (in this case, the value of a `Raw` variable is a sequence of unit values). If an alphabet is defined, we instead define the boundary value `VALUE_LEGAL` where all unit values are drawn from the alphabet. Three additional symbols represent `Raw` values where all unit values except one are drawn from the alphabet. The invalid value is either at the beginning (`!VALUE_ILLEGAL_START`), end (`!VALUE_ILLEGAL_END`) or a random location (`!VALUE_ILLEGAL_RAND`).

IPv4 `IPv4` variables in `Netzob` may define a network that generated addresses shall be restricted to. If a network is defined, the boundary values `VALUE_HOST` and `!VALUE_ILLEGAL` represent a random host within and outside the requested network, respectively. Additionally, `!VALUE_BROADCAST` and `!VALUE_NET` represent the broadcast and network address, which are almost always seen as invalid.

If the network is not defined, the ranges defined by RFC 5735 [6] are used to determine boundary values. This includes the localhost address 127.0.0.1 (`VALUE_LOCALHOST`), an entirely random public IP (`VALUE_PUBLIC`), and the broadcast address 255.255.255.255 (`!VALUE_BROADCAST`). Random host addresses in random private networks (`VALUE_PRIVATE`), the local link network 169.254.0.0/16 (`!VALUE_LINK`), a test network (`VALUE_TESTNET`) and the 6to4 relay anycast network 192.88.99.0/24 (`!VALUE_6T04`) are also available. Finally, random multicast addresses can be requested using the symbolic value `!VALUE_MULTICAST`, while a random reserved host address can be defined using `!VALUE_RESERVED`.

ASCII This type represents a string of characters. As such, the boundary values have been chosen to be “interesting” to some common functions applied to string processing. Strings are character sequences and thus made up of an alphabet,

which is thus used as a boundary value. This enables practitioners to model alphabetic (`ALPHABET_ALPHA`), alphanumeric (`ALPHABET_ALPHANUMERIC`), and hexadecimal (`ALPHABET_HEX`) strings. The value `ALPHABET_PRINTABLE` selects only printable ASCII characters, while `ALPHABET_UTF8` represents UTF-8 characters that may not be part of the ASCII range. Invalid strings are specified using the values `!ALPHABET_INVALID_UTF8` (which requests characters that can not appear in UTF-8) and `!ALPHABET_NUL_FIRST` (which causes the first character to always be the NUL character and is otherwise identical to `ALPHABET_ALPHA`).

Additionally, ASCII variables have a letter case; we utilize the values `CASE_UPPER` (all characters are uppercase), `CASE_LOWER` (all lowercase) and `CASE_RANDOM` (randomly mixed) to model this property.

Timestamp This type represents a timestamp; in addition to the current time (`VALUE_NOW`), boundary values may specify the epoch (i.e. second 0, `VALUE_ZERO`) and maximum (`VALUE_MAX`) of this type. Two further symbols define a random non-zero timestamp in the past (`VALUE_PAST`) and random non-maximum timestamp in the future (`VALUE_FUTURE`).

4.3 Input Parameter Model Generation

This Section describes how IPMs are derived from Netzob symbols and tackles our second **Research Question**. We extend all variables and types in Netzob with a method that inspects the properties of the current object and returns $\varrho = (\varpi, \phi : \varpi \rightarrow v)$, where ϖ is a set of identifiers (e.g. `Size`) and ϕ maps each of these identifiers to a set of properties v (e.g. the possible values for `Size`, such as `SIZE_MIN`). These properties are either boundary values (for data variables) or parameters (for node variables).

Two types of node variables are of particular interest: *Alt* and *Repeat* (see Section 4.1). We introduce the *Choice* property for Alt nodes (each of the values assigned to this property is the index of one of its child variables; *Choice* thus signals which of the child variables shall be used) and the *Count* property (the number of repetitions) for Repeat nodes.

During IPM generation, we descend through the message format's tree and recursively extract ϱ for all children of the current node while generating a unique prefix Ψ for each child. We additionally store a Python reference ι to the child object that allows us to directly access the object

Fig. 3: Visualization of a message format containing an Alt node

without iterating through the tree repeatedly. In this manner, we construct a set $\Sigma = \{(\Psi_1, \varrho_1, \iota_1), \dots, (\Psi_n, \varrho_n, \iota_n)\}$. This set Σ is then used to obtain an IPM: While the parameter names are generated using Ψ_i and each ϖ_{i_j} (for $i \in \{1, \dots, |\Sigma|\}$ and $j \in \{1, \dots, |\varpi_i|\}$), the parameter values are exactly the codomain v_{i_j} of each ϕ_{i_j} . The resulting IPM can then be used to construct a CA of a desired strength and later translated to concrete test cases as detailed in Section 4.4.

Notions of coverage. The semantics of the Alt variable pose a unique challenge. Consider the message format illustrated in Figure 3. It contains a single field, which in turn consists of a single Alt variable that can assume one of two values: Foo (ASCII) or Bar (Timestamp). A simplified IPM constructed using our approach is shown in Listing 1.2 (the boundary values shown are merely a representative sample).

```
Alt_Choice: Foo, Bar
Foo_Size: SIZE_MIN, SIZE_RAND, SIZE_MAX
Foo_Alphabet: ALPHABET_ALPHA, ALPHABET_HEX, ALPHABET_UTF8
Bar_Timestamp: VALUE_PAST, VALUE_NOW, VALUE_FUTURE
```

Listing 1.2: IPM for a fictional format

Figure 4 is an excerpt of a CA constructed from this IPM. Consider a row in this CA. When translating this test case, the final value of the Alt variable will be chosen based on its Choice parameter and all properties of the selected child variable. However, the properties of all

Alt_Choice	Foo_Size	Foo_Alphabet	Bar_Timestamp
Foo	SIZE_MIN	ALPHABET_ALPHA	VALUE_PAST
Foo	SIZE_RAND	ALPHABET_HEX	VALUE_NOW
Foo	SIZE_MAX	ALPHABET_UTF8	VALUE_FUTURE
Bar	SIZE_MIN	ALPHABET_HEX	VALUE_FUTURE
Bar	SIZE_RAND	ALPHABET_UTF8	VALUE_PAST
Bar	SIZE_MAX	ALPHABET_ALPHA	VALUE_NOW

other children of the Alt node will have no effect, as their value will not be used. This phenomenon is detrimental to the effective coverage achieved by the resulting test set. We refer to this scenario as *component-limited coverage*, as some components of the CA are ignored during translation. To alleviate this issue, we introduce a modified approach:

- Instead of a single IPM, two IPMs are created; one contains properties of data variables, while the other contains properties of node variables (including Alt and Repeat). We refer to these models as the *type IPM* and *node IPM* and their associated CAs as *type CA* and *node CA*.
- During translation, instead of iterating over the rows of just one CA, the cartesian product of the type CA and node CA is used. This remedies the issue of component-limited coverage, as every possible choice of each Alt variable is combined with each row of the type CA.

We refer to this approach as the *split-metavariable coverage*, as the parameters of the node CA can be seen as a form of metavariable that modifies the interpretation of the type CA.

Node variables that have other node variables as children add another layer of complexity. Consider a Repeat variable that encapsulates an Alt variable. Fixing the number of repetitions and the choice of child node means that for every repetition, the choice of child node remains the same. This may be detrimental to the fault detection capabilities of the test set. The naive solution would be to introduce an additional metavariable that encodes the choice of Alt variable for each repetition. Unfortunately, this drastically increases the number of required test cases, as this new metavariable would have to take a vast amount of values. We thus leave the topic of *full nested coverage* as future work.

4.4 Covering Array Translation

The CA translation utilizes the generated CA(s) and the model Σ (see Section 4.3). Abstract values for all primitive types (represented by rows of the type CA) are translated first before moving on to the translation of variables (based on the node CA). As Algorithm 1 shows, the translation takes the Netzob message format S , the generated type CA CA_t and optionally the node CA CA_n as its input and returns the set of translated concrete messages. If component-limited coverage is utilized, CA_n is empty.

The function `generate_ipm(S)` and the structure of Σ are described in Section 4.3. The Netzob message format S allows the assignment of concrete values to the properties of data and node variables. The functions `translate_types(S, r_t)` and `translate_nodes(S, r_n)` transform the symbolic values contained in row r_t (contained in CA_t) or r_n (taken from CA_n) to concrete values and assign the result to the respective objects in S . Netzob can automatically generate protocol messages (i.e. sequences of bits ready to be transmitted over a network) based on these data; the function `generate_message(S)` utilizes this capability.

Algorithm 1 CA translation algorithm

```

function TRANSLATE_CA( $S, CA_t, CA_n$ )
   $\Sigma \leftarrow$  generate_ipm( $S$ )
   $T \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
  if  $|CA_n| == 0$  then                                      $\triangleright$  Component-limited coverage
     $CA_n \leftarrow \{\emptyset\}$                                 $\triangleright$  Create fake single-row  $CA_n$ 
  end if
  for all  $r_t \in CA_t$  do
     $S \leftarrow$  translate_types( $S, r_t$ )                      $\triangleright$  Set type values
    for all  $r_n \in CA_n$  do
       $S \leftarrow$  translate_nodes( $S, r_n$ )                    $\triangleright$  Populate nodes
       $T \leftarrow T \cup$  generate_message( $S$ )
    end for
  end for
  return  $T$ 
end function

```

Fig. 5: Message format tree for TFTP Read Request (RRQ) message

4.5 Example

To illustrate our approach, we detail the steps used to translate a Netzob specification of the TFTP [30] Read Request (RRQ) message to an IPM, generate a CA, and translate the resulting test set to concrete messages. As the first work with this feature set, we leave a large-scale evaluation as future work. For reasons of brevity, our example focuses on component-limited coverage.

To read a file from a server, the RRQ message type (visualized in Figure 5) is used. Besides the 16-bit opcode field (0x1 for RRQ), it is comprised of a file name and a mode, which can be set to either `octet`, `netascii`, or `mail`. In Netzob, we can implement this message type as shown in Listing 1.3 (in practice, the format is inferred from traffic). The resulting IPM is shown in Listing 1.4. An excerpt of the resulting CA generated using PICT is given in Listing 1.5.

```

opcode = Field(name="OpCode", domain=Raw('\x0001'))
filename = Field(name="File", domain=ASCII(nbChars=(1,256)))
filename_term = Field(name="Filename_Terminator", domain=Raw('\x00'))
mode = Field(name="mode", domain=(Alt(["netascii", "octet", "mail"])))
mode_term = Field(name="Mode_Terminator", domain=Raw('\x00'))
tftpRrq = Symbol(name="RRQ", fields=[opcode, filename, filename_term, mode, mode_term])
tftpRrq.build_ipm('/tmp/tftp_rrq_ipm')
  
```

Listing 1.3: TFTP RRQ message format in Netzob

```

RRQ_File_params_Size: SIZE_MIN,SIZE_RAND,SIZE_MAX
RRQ_File_params_Alphabet: ALPHABET_ALPHA,ALPHABET_ALPHANUMERIC,ALPHABET_HEX,
  ↳ ALPHABET_PRINTABLE,ALPHABET_UTF8,~ALPHABET_INVALID_UTF8,~ALPHABET_NUL_FIRST
RRQ_File_params_LetterCase: CASE_UPPER,CASE_LOWER,CASE_RANDOM
RRQ_mode__params_ALT_CHOICE: 0,1,2
  
```

Listing 1.4: TFTP RRQ IPM

```

RRQ_File_params_Size RRQ_File_params_Alphabet RRQ_File_params_LetterCase
  ↳ RRQ_mode__params_ALT_CHOICE
SIZE_MIN ALPHABET_HEX CASE_UPPER 2
SIZE_MIN ALPHABET_ALPHANUMERIC CASE_LOWER 1
SIZE_MAX ALPHABET_UTF8 CASE_RANDOM 0
  
```

Listing 1.5: Excerpt of a CA created for the TFTP RRQ format

Listing 1.6 shows the process of translating this CA into concrete messages and truncated example output. Note that the third message is shortened.

```
[x for x in tftpRrq.specialize_from_ca('/var/tmp/tftp_rrq_ca')]
b'\x0001A\x00mail\x00',
b'\x0001r\x00octet\x00',
b'\x0001\x98\xbe\x92\xe\xb1\xc8...\xc8\xb8\x00netascii\x00',
```

Listing 1.6: TFTP Read Request message translation

5 Conclusion

This work investigates methods to reverse engineer specifications for network protocols from traffic traces, generate IPMs, and translate the contents of the constructed CAs to concrete messages. Our work advances two key areas: Modeling of (possibly unknown) input formats and the translation of abstract CAs to concrete messages. To the best of our knowledge, it is the first work that combines PRE with the automated construction of IPMs. It further identifies avenues for future work by hinting at shortcomings of coverage definitions.

A sizable body of work provides solid mathematical foundations for and demonstrates the practical applicability of CT methods. Nevertheless, their real-world adoption is limited, as significant barriers to entry remain. While the technical innovation presented in this work is straightforward, we aim to provide an impetus for further research advancing the state of the art and enabling streamlined industrial use, including a rigorous evaluation of CT methods – such as ours – regarding their accuracy, performance and utility in real-world processes and novel approaches to bridge the gap between research and practice.

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